

EFFECT OF CERAMIC PARTICLE SIZE ON PERFORMANCE OF RESIN MATRIX COMPOSITE FRICTION MATERIAL

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the effect of SiO₂ particles size on the friction mechanisms of friction materials was investigated. Five different size scales (10 μm, 80 μm, 180-700 μm, 700 μm-2.0 mm and 3.0 mm) were selected to prepare non-commercial friction materials. The worn surfaces, fade resistance, wear of materials and wear of matched discs, were investigated. Results showed that the particle size has a significant influence on the friction mechanisms. The fade resistance increases with the reinforced particles size. In addition, oversized particles improve the wear resistance of materials, but without causing excessive disc wear.

1 INTRODUCTION

Non-asbestos organic (NAO) friction materials have been widely used for many years in the braking field. The general reduction in braking efficiency resulted from degradation of organic components at high temperatures (fade phenomenon) is one of the most important problems for NAO friction materials application [1]. Ceramic reinforcements have been proved useful for improving the fade performance of friction materials due to the great thermal stability at high temperatures [2]. The size of ceramic particles plays a significant role in the fade performance [3]. For instance, H. Jang and his team researched the size effect of zircon particles (1-150 μm) on the friction stability, the oscillation of friction force, and wear resistance of the brake linings [2]. The publication [4] studied the effect of silicon carbide particles size (3-40 μm) on the fade performance and friction layer formation. In addition, J. Bijwe et al. also carried out a research on nano-abrasives [5]. Based on these studies, some conclusions were drawn that fine particles (smaller than 100 μm) usually work through a three-body interaction, while coarse particles (larger than 150 μm) can develop into contact plateaus by themselves and usually work through a two-body abrasive mode.

But it must be noted that the size scales of particles in previous investigations were no larger than 200 μm. Although the size of particles in the report [6] reached 500 μm, these particles were external (not included in friction materials). In addition, most of those efforts were focused on the fade resistance, wear of materials and wear of discs. But few efforts were made to explore the roles of particles in friction mechanisms.

In the present work, the size effect of SiO₂ particles on friction mechanisms was systematically investigated. Five non-commercial specimens containing particles with different size scales were prepared. The friction testing was conducted under constant speed, load and temperature. The friction mechanisms as a function of particles were studied by observing the worn surfaces. In addition, a simple physical model was firstly developed to give a quantitative comprehension of the friction coefficient of materials reinforced with large particles. The feasibility of the model across a range of formulations and operating conditions was verified through experiments.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Preparation of Materials

Five different size scales of SiO₂ particles (10 μm, 80 μm, 180–700 μm, 700 μm–2.0 mm, and 3.0 mm) were selected to prepare non-commercial composite friction materials. The volume fraction of particles is 36%. The composition of the resin matrix is given in Table 1. The relative amount of each ingredient except the binders is similar to most commercial friction materials. The as-received mixture was molded via hot-press. Six composite specimens P₀, P_{0.01}, P_{0.08}, P_{0.18–0.7}, P_{0.7–2.0}, and P_{3.0} were prepared in the present study.

This composite friction material consists of two components, i.e. resin matrix and particles. The volume fraction of particles is 36%. The composition of the resin matrix in this composite material is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Composition of the resin matrix in friction materials (vol. %)

Category	Ingredient	Amount (%)
Binders	Phenolic resin	31.5
	Rubber	12.2
Reinforcements	Carbon fibers	10.5
Functional filler	Vermiculite	9.7
Space filler	Barite	32.5
Lubricant	Graphite	3.6

2.2 Experiments

The friction test was performed on a JF 151 constant speed friction test machine. The constant test speed of the rub zone was 7.5 m/s. The schematic diagram of JF 151 friction tester and the test procedure are illustrated in Fig. 1. The constant normal load of 0.98 MPa was applied on the specimens. A gray iron disc with the nominal radius of 150 mm was employed as the counter disc. Two specimens (with a dimension of 25 mm × 25 mm × 6 mm) and the counter disc were all scraped with 600 # SiC paper. Two stages were involved in the procedure, i.e. running-in stage and test stage.

The average friction coefficient was recorded at the constant testing temperatures of 100, 150, 200, 250, 300 and 350 °C, respectively. The test was carried out for 5000 rotations at each temperature. The temperature was controlled through a heating device. The temperature was measured via a thermocouple which touched lightly against the sliding interface centerline of the disc with a force of 0.1 N.

Fig. 1 The schematic diagram of JF151 friction tester and the test procedure

The wear of the materials and the matched discs was evaluated by measuring the reduction in thickness before and after the whole test. In order to ensure good data accuracy and repeatability, each test was repeated five times. The worn surfaces of the specimens were observed by SEM (Zeiss - SUPARR 55) with an energy dispersive spectrometer (EDS) to understand the wear mechanisms.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Particle size effect on worn surfaces

Fig. 2 shows the worn surfaces of specimens with different reinforced particle size. When the particles size is 10 μm , the worn surfaces are characterized by some contact plateaus (Fig. 2a). These plateaus were formed by compacted debris from both materials and discs under pressure and shear force. Almost all of the friction behavior happened on these plateaus. Thus a conclusion can be drawn that particles of this size scale played an important role in the friction force by participating in the formation of plateaus.

For the specimen P0.08 (Fig. 2b), the worn surfaces are very rough, and many free particles can be observed. This could be due to the fact that the particles of 80 μm were easily released from the resin matrix and arrested at the rubbing interface. Some violent mechanical interactions between these particles and the friction pair could provide a considerable resistance against the sliding. This is also known as the three-body abrasive mode [8, 9].

Fig. 2 Worn surfaces of different specimens after friction test: (a) P_{0.01}; (b) P_{0.08}; (c) P_{0.18-0.7}; (d) P_{3.0}

In Fig. 2c, the worn surfaces of specimens P_{0.18-0.7} are characterized by some small pits and large contact plateaus. These pits were induced by the release of finer particles from the resin matrix, while these plateaus were formed by the larger particles themselves. Firstly, the released finer particles could contribute a lot to the friction force with a three-body abrasive mode. Secondly, the deformation resistance of the disc could resist against the sliding when the sharp edges or corners of the larger particles caused a plowing to the disc, which is known as a two-body abrasive mode [9]. Additionally, an adhesive friction force could generate on those plateaus. This is supported by the publications [7, 8] which held that adhesive friction always happens at the clean rubbing interface through intermolecular force and develops an interfacial shear stress to resist against the sliding of friction couple.

When the particles size is 3 mm (Fig. 2d), these oversized particles are firmly embedded into the resin matrix and rise over the lowland. Furthermore, few pits or free particles can be observed on the surfaces. Compared to P_{0.18-0.7}, the friction for P_{3.0} was dominated by the two-body abrasive mode and the adhesive friction.

3.2 Particle size effect on friction performance

The average friction coefficient as a function of particle size is given in Fig. 3. It firstly increases and then decreases with increasing particle size. This was related to the roles of particles in the friction. The transformation of friction mechanisms with particle size is illustrated in Fig. 2, and roughly divided into four regions. The fine particles of 10 μm worked through participating in the formation of contact plateaus. When the size was about 80 μm , the particles contributed a significant amount to the friction with a three-body abrasive mode. With the increase of particle size, a two-body abrasive mode

and an adhesive friction occurred. Finally, when the size scale reached about 3.0 mm, the three-body abrasive mode disappeared and was replaced by the adhesive friction and the two-body abrasive mode dominating the friction.

Fig. 3 The size effect of particles on the friction coefficient and friction mechanisms during the test stage

The wear of the friction materials and matched discs is presented in Fig. 4. It can be seen that the introduction of oversized particles improves the wear resistance of materials. While the introduction of fine particles increases the wear of materials.

In such case of dry sliding, at least two wear mechanisms are identified as responsible for the wear of friction materials, i.e. abrasive wear and adhesive wear [5]. With respect to the abrasive wear, the harder asperities penetrating into the softer material results in the plowing or scoring of the softer surface [10]. For the specimen P3.0, presenting the best wear resistance, it can be attributed to the inherent hardness of ceramic particles. As stated by Eriksson [11], ceramic particles with the considerable hardness could develop into primary plateaus at the rubbing interface, which reduced the abrasive wear of the friction materials caused by the counter disc. With respect to the adhesive wear, it happens when the strength of adhesive junctions is greater than the shear strength of the two mating materials. For the specimen P3.0, the adhesive junctions mainly generated at the rubbing interface between the disc and the particles. And the ceramic particle possesses excellent shear strength, which could prevent itself being removed with the adhesive mode.

The wear of composite friction materials with finer particles is much higher as compared to P3.0, even though they also contain particles. The poor particle-matrix cohesion might be the key factor. This can be confirmed by the worn surfaces of P0.18-0.70 in Figs. 2 (b) and 2 (c). Some pits caused by the release of fine particles from the matrix can be observed obviously. Firstly, the release of particles resulted in the direct wear of the friction materials. Secondly, parts of the released particles were arrested at the rubbing interface and then crushed into finer debris, which enhanced the wear of materials with a three-body abrasive mode [5].

Fig. 4 Wear of friction specimens (a) and matched discs (b) as a function of reinforced particle size

In Fig. 4(b), the wear performance of matched discs changes with the friction materials. The addition of particles results in a more severe wear of matched discs. But for sample P_{3,0}, the wear of the matched disc is not as serious as anticipated. This is because the particles rise above the rest of the surface of samples with fine particles. Particles with sharp edges and corners are related to the wear performance of the matched disc. The particle abraded the disc with a two-body abrasive wear mode, which was responsible for the severe wear of the disc. One reason was that most of the load could concentrate on these rising plateaus. And then, the pressure applied on the particles was enhanced indirectly. Consequently, the increasing pressure enhanced the abrasive wear mechanism. One reason might be that the shorter edge length and fewer corners for oversized particles directly weaken the plowing and cutting to the counter disc. Another reason might be that a conformable face-face contact between the oversized particles and the disc reduced the influences of sharp edges.

3.3 Particle size effect on fade rate

Fig. 5(a) displays the friction coefficient of different specimens as a function of temperature. For specimen P₀, the friction coefficient fluctuates more severely with increasing temperatures. Its fade rate is very high. In contrast, the introduction of particles improves the friction stability of materials, especially at the high temperatures. And the fade resistance increases with the increasing particles size. The friction coefficient of P_{3,0} keeps stable as a function of temperature.

In order to evaluate the fade performance of friction materials in the present work, the fade rate ω is specially given as follows,

$$\omega = \frac{\mu_{max} - \mu_{350^{\circ}\text{C}}}{\mu_{max}} \times 100\%$$

where μ_{max} stands for the maximum friction coefficient during the whole test process, while $\mu_{350^{\circ}\text{C}}$ stands for the friction coefficient at 350 °C.

Fig. 5 (a) The friction coefficient and (b) fade rate of different specimens as a function of temperature

The fade is caused by the degradation of organic ingredients at elevated temperatures. With regard to the nature of fade, Blau and McLaughlin [12] proposed that high rubbing interface temperature can lead to a decrease in shear strength of the pad and consequently a decrease in friction force which induces fade. In fact, the shear force is developed either by the intermolecular force or by other forms of bonding force at the real contact area, which resists against the relative sliding for the friction couple [7, 8]. Therefore, it can be inferred that the larger contact area between the oversized particles and the disc is one crucial factor for improving the fade resistance of P_{3,0}. More adhesive junctions can be established on the real contact area, resulting in the increase of shear force [8]. In contrast, less real contact area can be formed in P₀ ascribed to the lack of solid primary plateaus [9, 13]. Maybe composite materials P_{0.18-0.70} and P_{0.70-2.0} also have large nominal contact area, but the fade resistance is still poorer as compared to P_{3,0}. This can be explained by the poor particle-matrix cohesion for the fine particles. The shear force established on the fine particles could not be maintained effectively due to the easy release of fine particles from the resin matrix.

In addition, some publications attributed the root of fade to the decreasing deformation resistance of materials at the rubbing interface at the elevated temperature [14]. The deformation component and

plowing component of the friction force is closely related to the elastic hysteresis and plastic deformation of materials at the contact zones [8, 10]. Based on this view, the decreasing elastic and plastic properties of materials at the rubbing interface induced by the high temperature is a key factor for the fade phenomenon. In this respect, the great thermal stability of oversized particles at high temperatures may be an important reason for the good fade resistance of P_{3.0}. However, the poor particle-matrix cohesion for fine particles could weaken this advantage, which is responsible for the poorer fade resistance of P_{0.18-0.70} and P_{0.70-2.0}.

It should be pointed out that the friction film also played significant roles in the fade performance when a friction film had been created at the rubbing interface, and this will be discussed in the following section.

4 CONCLUSION

In this paper, oversized particles were used to improve the fade performance of friction materials. The worn surfaces, fade resistance, wear of materials and wear of matched discs, were investigated. The particle size has a significant influence on the friction mechanisms. The fade resistance increases with the reinforced particles size. In addition, oversized particles improve the wear resistance of materials, but without causing excessive disc wear.

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